

Driving Employee Creativity with Empowering Leadership: The Role of Happiness at Work and Intrinsic Motivation

Wimby Wandary

Faculty of Economics and Business, Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin, Indonesia
Faculty of Economics and Business, Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Indonesia
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7949-5891>
wimbywandary@ulm.ac.id

Asri Laksmi Riani

Faculty of Economics and Business, Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Indonesia
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9812-6493>

Mugi Harsono

Faculty of Economics and Business, Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Indonesia
<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-4303-7307>

Hidajat Hendarsjah

Faculty of Economics and Business, Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta, Indonesia
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2843-2521>

Abstract

Background: Modern organisations' growing emphasis on innovation and adaptability highlights the need for leadership approaches that promote creativity. Empowering leadership (EL) has gained recognition as a promising yet under-explored approach to enhancing employee creativity (EC), particularly through its impact on positive emotional states and motivational pathways.

Objective: This research aims to deepen the understanding of the EL-EC relationship through the lens of Social Exchange Theory (SET). This theoretical framework explores the mechanisms by which happiness at work (HAW) and intrinsic motivation (IM) mediate the relationship between EL and EC.

Methodology: Literatures were reviewed, focusing more on mediation and moderation effects in EL studies. This conceptual study examines 29 relevant papers to provide an overview on research

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variables. Inclusion criteria applied are: articles that focus on EL and its impact on EC, SET as theoretical framework, and it published within the last decade in English.

Results: This research emphasises the importance of EL in enhancing EC but asserts that the best results are achieved when HAW and IM are considered as key elements supporting this relationship.

Conclusion: The proposed model posits that EC is enhanced by EL, while IM capitalises on the impact of EL when HAW mediates the primary relationship. The model addresses existing gaps in previous research and offers insights for leaders on how to enhance creativity levels.

Unique contribution: This framework could broaden the scope of research on empowering leadership by offering a more nuanced perspective on leadership styles and workplace creativity. It also emphasises understanding and addressing employee happiness in specific workplace contexts.

Key recommendation: Future research should empirically test this framework and investigate the influence of contextual factors related to happiness on the observed relationship.

Keywords: Empowering leadership, employee creativity, happiness at work, intrinsic motivation, SET.

Introduction

Employee creativity (EC) is an important element in ensuring long-term competitive advantage in all kinds of private organisations for its potential to drive innovation, enhance problem-solving, and strengthen competitiveness in pursuit of organisational success (Bousinakis & Halkos, 2021). Organisations can nurture creativity by way of initiative-taking, recognition of creative employees, and cultivation of cooperative work environments to improve their performance (Zaitouni & Ouakouak, 2018). Employee creativity improves performance, success, and company survival (T. Ahmad et al., 2023b; Zaitouni & Ouakouak, 2018). It also boosts satisfaction and positive work culture (Bousinakis & Halkos, 2021).

Leaders play a crucial role in fostering employee creativity as they create supportive environments that encourage innovation. Employees are most creative when leaders provide support, care for their needs, and offer constructive feedback (Zaitouni & Ouakouak, 2018). A systematic review (2009-2023) highlights that leader-related factors are key to enhancing creativity, with non-controlling leadership styles being the most effective (Ersoy, 2023)(Ersoy, 2023) with creative employees exhibiting traits such as open-mindedness, risk-taking, and adaptability. For organisations to persist and flourish in the 21st century, creative thinking is indispensable. and companies must support employees in developing these skills. Additionally, modern employees increasingly seek autonomy and flexibility (Chernyak-Hai & Rabenu, 2018).

Different leadership styles emphasise various aspects, which might not always support employee creativity (EC) (Ersoy, 2023). Aligning leadership styles with employee characteristics is crucial for enhancing workplace creativity. A study examines the premise that "empowerment fosters creativity" (Liu et al., 2020). Employee empowerment, characterised by sharing power and motivating employees, has a positive effect on performance, satisfaction, and productivity (A. Huang & Lee, 2022; Vu, 2020). Empowerment grants employee's autonomy, strengthens their decision-making flexibility, and increases their confidence. Empowering leadership addresses employees' needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, thereby increasing motivation and encouraging creativity (Kim, 2019). This leadership style fosters a supportive environment where employees are motivated to share innovative ideas. Furthermore, research by A. Lee et al. (2018)

demonstrates that empowering leadership has a positive impact on creativity at both the individual and team levels.

EL has emerged as a critical factor for fostering employee creativity and workplace satisfaction. EL enhances creativity through psychological empowerment, self-leadership, and work engagement (Joo et al., 2023). It fosters a positive work environment that enhances creativity, job satisfaction, employee engagement, and work-life balance through emotional commitment and a sense of responsibility for change. While studies show a positive relationship between EL and creativity (Ahmad et al., 2023b), some report no significant effect (Joo et al., 2023; Kim, 2019)(Joo et al., 2023; Kim, 2019). This study addresses these inconsistencies by incorporating mediating and moderating variables to clarify when and how EL influences creativity (Joo et al., 2023).

Homans' (1958) Social Exchange Theory (SET) views workplace relationships as reciprocal, where employees and organisations, represented by leaders, engage in mutually beneficial exchanges (Ahmad et al., 2023a). Empowering leadership fosters positive exchange by providing employees with autonomy and support, encouraging creativity in return for the leader's investment (Coyle-Shapiro & Diehl, 2018). Modern employees seeking autonomy and flexibility, respond positively to empowerment, which stimulates creativity and aligns with generational values (Chernyak-Hai & Rabenu, 2018). SET highlights the importance of positive social exchanges in enhancing employee engagement, job satisfaction, and performance, to guide managers to create supportive environments that foster organisational success (Y. Lee, 2022; Shahidan et al., 2016). Research shows that EL has a significant impact on EC, although the strength of this effect varies. While some studies highlight a strong link between EL and creativity (Ahmad et al., 2023b). Others report a weaker connection (Peng et al., 2023)(Peng et al., 2023). Intrinsically motivated employees demonstrate greater creativity, especially when granted autonomy and supported by their leaders. However, this creativity thrives mainly in environments that encourage creative expression. Intrinsic motivation, driven by vision, values, and passion (Ryan & Deci, 2000), plays a key role in effective leadership. This study aims to identify the specific conditions under which empowering leadership is most effective in fostering employee creativity.

Research on factors influencing EC indicates a multifaceted relationship between leadership style and creativity. Within the framework of SET, a leader's psychological investment can influence employees' subjective well-being. Both positive and negative emotions play a significant role in shaping creativity (Amabile et al., 2005; Liu et al., 2022). Leaders' support drives positive feelings at the workplace – HAW, which eventually encourages employees to do their best by being creative in performing their jobs. This study puts HAW as a mediator for EL – EC impact, which has not been widely explored. EL promotes employee satisfaction, engagement, and attachment, which in turn boosts creativity (Chernyak-Hai & Rabenu, 2018). Furthermore, modern employees, who increasingly seek autonomy and flexibility, are happier and more productive when their needs are met.

In short, EC is essential for organisations to stay competitive. It drives innovation, problem-solving, and overall company performance. Leaders play a key role in boosting EC by creating supportive environments where employees feel empowered. Non-controlling leadership styles that offer constructive feedback and creativity being nurtured at workplace. EL stands out as a crucial factor in fostering EC, as it enhances job satisfaction, engagement, and work-life balance (Joo et

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al., 2023; Salas-Vallina et al., 2018). Psychological empowerment, self-leadership, and overall workplace happiness enhanced by EL which well aligns with the modern employee's desire for autonomy and flexibility in advanced (Kim, 2019). In order to optimise creativity and performance level, leadership styles must consider one's embedded traits. SET is in favour of facilitating us with the insight into the leader-employee reciprocal relationship. The theory illustrates how EL drives employees to contribute their creativity in exchange for their perceived autonomy, support, and recognition. These relationships build a positive workplace exchange.

Nevertheless, there's a significant impact of EL on EC; there were inconsistencies, which provide an opportunity to consider the dynamics of the relationship in a specific context. It can represent challenges and opportunities, especially when it relates to individual motivation, the intrinsic motivation (IM), which is an important aspect in fostering creativity in conducive environments. This study seeks to understand how EL boosts EC, integrating Happiness at Work (HAW) as a mediator, as it is not yet fully explored. Gaining a better understanding on these relationships is crucial to improve employee well-being and productivity at workplace. Thus, it is important to bridge the gap in understanding of the mediating and moderating roles in the relationship between empowerment leadership (EL) and employee creativity (EC). In this context, this study aims to examine how happiness at work (HAW) acts as a mediator and how intrinsic motivation (IM) acts as a moderator to strengthen the relationship between EL and EC.

Propositions Development

Social-exchange Theory (SET)

Social Exchange Theory (SET) was credited to sociologist George C. Homans in the late 1950s, which focuses on people's interaction within small groups and communities. The perspective on social relationships is based on a utilitarian and sociological principle. Homans posit that an ongoing exchange is the form of social behaviour, where individuals seek to maximise their benefits and minimize the costs (Muldoon et al., 2018). At core, the theory manifest economic principles into social interactions, assuming that people consider more on the potential benefits and its costs before decide to engage in a relationship. The theorist views in a reductionist approach that shed a light on individual interactions, the resources exchange, rewards, and sacrifices (Davlembayeva & Alamanos, 2022). At its core, SET views that when exchanging rewards, resources, and benefits within their social relationships, people seek balance and fairness. The exchange is based on each party evaluations on their sacrifices/investment to their expected gain in return. The reciprocity principle is key to keep fairness and balance at place in relationships, since both involved party expect on the perceived social, emotional, and economic rewards. This reciprocal relationship in exchange the basis for SET's sociological framework. The social exchange process Davlembayeva and Alamanos (2022) depict in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Davlembayeva and Alamanos (2022) Social-exchange Process

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According to SET, individuals involved in a certain relationship that aimed to maximize benefits and minimize the costs at all forms (i.e., tangible rewards and intangible factors like social approval, respect, and emotional satisfaction) (Davlembayeva & Alamanos, 2022). As relationships develop, how fair these exchanges feel becomes essential for their longevity. If one party perceives an imbalance in the exchange, it can lead to dissatisfaction or even the end of the relationship.

El and EC

Research has shown that EL plays a key role in boosting EC as highlighted by several studies (Ahmad et al., 2023b; Chow, 2017; Peng et al., 2023). EL fosters an environment that encourages innovation by giving employees the autonomy and authority to make decisions. Although the empowerment process demands time and persistence, it results in improved performance and fewer bureaucratic obstacles. The psychological and motivational advantages of EL are key to its success in fostering creativity. In today's workforce, employees increasingly desire autonomy, flexibility, and diversity, making EL a particularly effective strategy for encouraging creativity (Chernyak-Hai and Rabenu, 2018). Research consistently supports the positive relationship between EL and EC (Ahmad et al., 2023b; Chow, 2017). From the SET perspective, the reciprocal nature of EL strengthens the social exchange between leaders and employees. SET posits that individuals engage in relationships where mutual benefit is expected and that positive exchanges (such as support, trust, and empowerment) generate a sense of obligation and commitment (Homans, 1958). In this context, when leaders empower employees, they provide resources (autonomy, trust, support) that employees perceive as valuable, creating a cycle of reciprocity. Employees, in turn, feel motivated to reciprocate with increased creativity, commitment, and higher performance. This mutually beneficial exchange not only promotes employee well-being but also enhances organisational success, reinforcing the importance of empowering leadership in fostering a creative and productive work environment. Thus, the 1st proposed proposition is: EL positively impacts EC in the social exchange mechanism.

The Mediating role of HAW

This study proposes happiness at work (HAW) as a mediator in the relationship between EL and EC. Theoretical perspectives underscore that emotional states significantly influence creativity (Amabile et al., 2005; Amabile & Khaire, 2008). As their study have demonstrated, positive emotions, such as happiness, enhance cognitive flexibility, exploration, and the generation of diverse, innovative ideas. Conversely, negative emotions can either constrain creativity by narrowing focus or stimulate creativity by promoting problem-solving and detailed attention. This complexity highlights that the effects of emotions on creativity are shaped by factors such as emotion type, intensity, and duration.

Research on EL and HAW has yielded mixed results. For instance, Ghadi & Almanaga'h (2020) and Salas-Vallina & Alegre (2021) found no significant impact in public sector contexts, while L. Huang (2023) observed positive effects in banking and healthcare sectors. This variability underscores the importance of considering sector-specific dynamics. In the private sector, where market-driven demands prevail, fostering HAW through EL may more effectively drive creativity (Salas-Vallina & Alegre, 2021).

From the Social Exchange Theory perspective, the reciprocal nature of leader-employee interactions plays a crucial role in nurturing positive emotional states and, in turn, stimulating

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innovative behaviours. SET posits that individuals engage in social exchanges expecting mutual benefits (Homans, 1958). In the context of EL, leaders provide support, trust, and autonomy to employees, which are perceived as valuable resources. Employees, feeling empowered, reciprocate with increased creativity and engagement. This reciprocal relationship nurtures positive emotional states such as HAW, which enhances creativity (Xu et al., 2023). Therefore, under EL, HAW will mediate the effect of EL on EC, particularly in the contemporary organisations where creativity is a critical driver for success. Thus, the 2nd proposed proposition is: Happiness at work mediates the impact of EL on EC.

The Moderating role of IM

SET emphasises the mutual benefits in relationships, where individuals engage in exchanges expecting to maximise rewards while minimising costs (Homans, 1958). However, IM is a critical variable that operates outside the core mechanisms of SET and beyond the direct control of EL. While EL creates an environment of support, autonomy, and trust, which encourages positive social exchanges, IM plays a foundational role in driving individual creativity and engagement that cannot be solely attributed to leadership behaviours.

As Ryan and Deci (2000) define, IM is “the inherent tendency to seek out novelty and challenges, to extend and exercise one’s capacities, to explore, and to learn,” driving individuals to engage in activities for internal satisfaction rather than external rewards. This internal motivation drives toward growth, adaptability, and learning about anything outside the realm of influence. For instance, EL was significantly related to EC outcomes (Ahmad et al., 2023a; Kim, 2019; Peng et al., 2023), but the strength of this correlation can be weak. This difference indicates that IM can act as a moderating factor, and thus a more nuanced understanding is possible.

Employees who have strong intrinsic motivation (IM) are prone to exhibiting creativity as they genuinely like their job and are therefore greater eager to put in the effort for challenging tasks (Chow, 2017). IM plays an essential function when it comes to creativity, innovation, and personal happiness. It also enhances the effectiveness of Empowering Leadership (EL) through increasing staff engagement and performance. By encouraging autonomy, competence, and connection, IM fosters an environment where creativity can flourish, making it an essential component for the success of individuals as well as organisations.

Thus, while Empowering Leadership (EL) establishes a favourable condition for creativity by providing autonomy and support, Intrinsic Motivation (IM) enhances this process by driving one's inherent desire and personal satisfaction, which makes it an essential element that works beyond the direct control of EL. Recognising and nurturing IM alongside EL is therefore necessary for pushing innovation and enabling businesses to remain competitive and adaptive in volatile

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circumstances. Thus, the suggested proposition is: IM will moderate the impact of EL on EC. Lastly, considering the 3 propositions, the suggested framework for this study is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The proposed conceptual model

Discussion

The integration of HAW, IM, and EL within the context of SET offers a more nuanced understanding of how leadership EC. While SET focuses on reciprocal relationships between leaders and employees, emphasising mutual benefits and exchanges, HAW and IM serve as critical mediating and moderating factors in this dynamic.

SET posits that EL fosters positive social exchanges by providing employees with support, trust, autonomy, and resources, which they perceive as valuable. In turn, these positive exchanges create a sense of mutual obligation and commitment (Homans, 1958). However, HAW plays a key role in mediating this relationship by enhancing the emotional well-being of employees. As Amabile et al. (2005) and Ryan and Deci (2000) suggest, positive emotional states like happiness boost cognitive flexibility, creativity, and innovation. When employees are happy at work, they are more likely to feel engaged, motivated, and open to exploring new ideas, which directly fosters creativity.

At the same time, IM further strengthens this process by acting as a moderating variable. Ryan and Deci (2000) define IM as “the inherent tendency to seek out novelty and challenges...to extend and exercise one’s capacities.” IM drives individuals to engage in an agenda for internal satisfaction rather than external rewards. Employees with high IM tend to be more creative because they enjoy their work and are intrinsically motivated to take on challenging tasks (Chow, 2017). Intrinsic motivation increases engagement, persistence, and productivity, essential for creativity, as well as the effectiveness of EL, resulting in more positive responses to leadership support and responses with innovative behaviours.

Hence, HAW and IM are not just secondary aspects but are important to comprehending how EL nurtures creativity. HAW mediates the connection between EL and EC by promoting positive feelings that elevate creative thinking. Meanwhile, IM moderates the impact of EL on creativity by improving employees' own motivation to engage in creative endeavours. This simultaneous focus on HAW and IM offers a more thorough view of how leadership may encourage creativity, indicating that both emotional wellness and intrinsic motivation are important for unleashing the full potential of EL.

In summary, HAW and IM are important elements in explaining both how as well as why EL builds EC. SET simply may not entirely capture the complexity of this relationship; therefore, integrating HAW and IM is recommended for a more comprehensive understanding. By acknowledging and nurturing both HAW and IM alongside EL, firms can foster a setting that promotes creativity, driving long-term innovation and success.

Limitations and Future Research Suggestions

The research model proposed in this study has not yet been subjected to empirical testing; therefore, the impact of each variable in its respective position in the proposed model remains to

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be determined. Further research is recommended to conduct tests where empirical approaches can be employed, such as quantitative surveys or experiments. Future research suggests using a longitudinal design to ascertain the development of the variables' influence over time.

This paper focused on the relationship between EL, EC, HAW and IM but did not yet consider contextual factors. Future research could expand the model by considering work environment factors, national culture differences, organisational culture, or other potential external variables that may influence employee creativity.

The model is not yet aware of the contextual concept of happiness, which is relevant to work or employment settings. It is recommended that future research consider the eudemonic and hedonic values on the happiness concept at the workplace. And finally, this study has not considered control variables, which may eliminate confounding effects and reduce estimation bias in the relationship between variables. Without considering control factors such as age, gender, work experience, industry type, or team size, the validity of the cause-and-effect relationship between the predictor (EL) and outcome (EC) may be affected, leading to less accurate interpretation of the results. Future research is recommended to include relevant control variables, such as individual characteristics (age, gender, education, work experience) or organisational characteristics (industry type, work culture, company size). This will help ensure that the research results reflect a more valid relationship between EL, HAW, IM, and EC.

Conclusion

This study suggests the essential function of the leadership concept (EL) is to increase creativity at work (EC), with happiness (HAW) serving as a mediator and personal motivation (IM) operating as a moderator. Within the SET perspective, the study aims to reveal how supportive, autonomous, and trustworthy interactions between leaders and employees promote positive feelings that fuel creativity. It implies that work conditions that foster HAW and IM, alongside EL, can significantly boost creativity, delivering essential information for organisations aiming to develop a culture of invention. Eventually, integrating HAW and IM inside the SET framework presents a comprehensive approach for enhancing EC, benefiting both individual employees and the firm as a whole.

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